

**DEVELOPMENT AND TRY OUT OF SOFT SKILL ENHANCEMENT
PROGRAMME FOR PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS OF UTTAR PRADESH:
ITS EFFECT ON TEACHING COMPETENCE**

***RESEARCH PROJECT REPORT
UNDER RESEARCH DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME***

***Submitted to
Directorate of Higher Education, Prayagraj
Through
Regional Office Higher Education, Meerut***

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(2024)

1.0.0 CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

National Education Policy 2020 envisions to make India a global knowledge superpower, the nation dreams skillful teachers and skillful students to face new challenges of the developing society. It is expected from the teacher education institutions that these institutions will develop teacher trainees in hard as well as soft skills. It has been observed that students/teacher trainees have good hard skills but when soft skills are evaluated, they are unable to express properly. Soft skills make prospective teachers to cope up with all the changes becoming in education system. New National Education Policy 2020 defines Good institution as the place where every student feels welcomed and cared for and the skills which are to be enriched here for holistic development of the learner are: communication, collaboration, scientific temper, creativity, digital literacy, multilingualism, critical training and social responsibility. Only then the skills can be developed in the students, when teachers are skilled first. But the recently developed teacher education curriculum applied in 2014 stresses on teaching competencies. The need of the hour is to give emphasis on soft skill development in teacher education curriculum.

To develop passionate, motivated, and professionally skilled teachers, sound base for soft skill development is necessary. Moreover, it is also mentioned in the policy that pedagogy is to be transformed as: activity-based learning, collaborative learning, group learning, peer tutoring, enjoyable and engaging learning and this shift in pedagogy calls for special provision of soft skill development in teacher education curriculum and designing training programs for enhancement of soft skills.

Roots of work on skills with reference to many professions can be seen during 1970s. In the report given by UNESCO in 1972, there is emphasis upon continued expansion of education and long-life education. Then the *Delors Report* (1996) formulated four principles identified as the Four Pillars of Education: Learning to Know, Learning to Do, Learning to Be and Learning to Live Together and emphasized the concept of lifelong learning in more comprehensive and updated way. In globalized economy, all the organizations depend on the capabilities of manpower and their collaborating abilities for the success. *Friedman* (2006) made a comprehensive analysis of skill requirements of workplace and identified some influences on changing patterns of work. He found that work is subdivided into such components that call for different skill levels. The individuals having knowledge and skills were demanded having a

greater focus on generic skills in education. Advanced organizations and institutions require more and more professionals furnished with a broad range of skills.

The word ‘Skill’ is defined by academicians and psychologists in various ways. The holistic approach believes that the word “Skill” usually refers to three levels of individual functioning: knowledge, attitude, and skills as given by Bloom et al. in terms of cognitive, affective and psychomotor domain (Bloom, 1956; Dave, 1970; Krathwohl, Bloom and Maria 1999; Simpson, 1966; Harrow, 1972).

In changing economy, it has been established that only knowledge is not sufficient for success in jobs; skill and attitude are equally important to perform a certain activity. **Drucker** (1999) has predicted that the most valuable asset in today’s knowledge economy will be well educated and skilled people (knowledge workers) and their productivity. Hard skills (specific for a certain type of task) and soft skills (personal attributes) both are essential for effective and competent job performance. Hard skills are technical, specific, and procedural while soft skills are attitudinal, behavioural, general, and non-technical in nature. Soft skills complement hard skills which are the technical requirements of a profession.

Various terms are used for soft skills in world as listed in table 1:

Table 1: Different names proposed to define Soft Skills - Maria Cinque

Name	Organization
Life skills	WHO,1993
Transversal skills	ISFOL,1998
Generic competences	Tuning project, 2000
Key competencies for a successful life and a well-functioning society	OECD, 2003;2012
Key competences for lifelong learning	UE, 2006
Transferable skills	RPIC-ViP, 2011
Future work skills	IFTF, 2010
Soft Skills for Talent	Manpower Group, 2014
Skills for Social Progress	OECD, 2015
21st century skills	Ananiadou & Claro, 2009; New National Educational Policy, 2020

In order to define and identify soft skills, it was found that different countries give a long list of workplace skills. There is not globally accepted list of soft skill and each discipline, educational sector and country defines soft skill according to their own requirements. *Philip and Chris* (1996) defined Soft skills as “Skills, abilities and traits that pertain to personality, attitude and behaviour rather than to formal or technical knowledge.” As defined in Career Opportunities, October 2002, “A soft skill refers to the cluster of personality traits, social graces, facility with language, personal habits, friendliness, and optimism that mark each of us to varying degrees. Persons who rank high in this cluster, with good soft skills, are generally the people that most employers want to hire. Soft skills complement hard skills, which are the technical requirements of a job. The ideal, of course, is someone strong in both job and personal skills.” The *Glossary of Education* defines 21st Century Skills as a broad set of knowledge, skills, work habits, and character traits that are believed— by educators, school reformers, college professors, employers, and others—to be critically important to success in today’s world. In simple terms, 21st Century Skills refer to the skills that are required to enable an individual to face the challenges of the 21st century world that is globally-active, digitally transforming, collaboratively moving forward, creatively progressing, seeking competent human-resource and quick in adopting changes.

On the basis of the historical development of 21st Century Skills, it can be stated that 21st century skills broadly consist of three main skill sets or 3 Ls - namely, Learning Skills, Life Skills and Literacy Skills. (CBSE, 2020)

- Learning Skills: skills required for the acquisition of new knowledge.
- Literacy Skills: skills that help in creating and gaining new knowledge through reading, media and digital resources
- Life Skills: skills required for successfully leading everyday life.

Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21), a coalition of business leaders and educators, proposed a Framework for 21st Century Learning, identified essential competencies and skills vital for success in twenty-first century work and life (P21, 2007a, 2011). These included ‘The 4Cs’ – communication, collaboration, critical thinking, and creativity, which are to be taught within the context of core subject areas and twenty-first century themes. This framework is based on the assertion that twenty-first century challenges will demand a broad skill set emphasizing core subject skills, social and cross-cultural skills, proficiency in languages other than English, and an understanding of the economic and political forces that affect societies.

These days, this term has been expanded itself to comprise categories (in the various lists of soft skills) that include (but not exhaust to):

- (a) Qualities including adaptability, courtesy, integrity, professionalism, and effectiveness, and values such as trustworthiness and work ethics (Wats and Wats, 2009; Touloumakos,2011; Robles,2012; Ballesteros-Sanchez et al; 2017);
- (b) Problem solving, decision making, analytical thinking / thinking skills, creativity/ innovation, manipulation of knowledge, critical judgment (Cimatti, 2016; Succi, 2019; Succi and Canovi, 2019; Thompson, 2019);
- (c) Leadership and managing skills (Crosbie,2005; Lazarus, 2013; Ballesteros-Sanchez et al, 2017), as well as self- awareness, managing oneself/coping skills (Cimatti, 2016; Cinque, 2017; Thompson, 2019);
- (d) Communication skills (Wats and Wats, 2009; Mitchell et al., 2010; Stevenson and Starkweather, 2010; Robles, 2012; Cinque, 2017) including elements of negotiation, conflict resolution, persuasion skills, and diversity (Bancino and Zevalkink,2007; Majid et al.,2012; Cinque, 2017; Succi and Canovi, 2019) as well as articulation work – that is orchestrating simultaneous interaction with people, information, and technology (see Hampson and Junor, 2009).
- (e) Other areas covered included cognitive ability or processes (Cimatti, 2016; Ballesteros-Sanchez et al., 2017; Thompson, 2019), ability to plan and achieve goals (Cimatti, 2016).

The skills in using technology, in particular digital skills, will be fundamental in most jobs to perform many tasks (Cinque, 2015). Furthermore, digital resources can help students to develop and train their Soft Skills, then they can be considered at the same time aims to be reached and tools to train, to develop and increase competences and capabilities.

Sasi and Anna (2004) identified the soft skills for prospective teachers as Effective Communication, Listening, Interpersonal Relationship, Time Management, Team Work and Problem Solving. *Kereluik et.al.* (2013) have identified three broad categories of knowledge teachers must possess to succeed in the 21st century: i) Foundational Knowledge with three key subcategories: core content knowledge, digital literacy, and cross-disciplinary knowledge; ii) Meta knowledge with three subcategories: Problem solving & critical thinking, communication and collaboration, and creativity & innovation; iii) Humanistic knowledge with three subcategories : Life/job skills/Leadership, cultural competence, and Ethical/Emotional

Awareness. *Ramesh and Ramesh* (2018) believe that soft skills essentially consist of three dimensions as Attitude, Communication and Etiquette. Attitude is about having the right mental make-up and a desire to interact with the people and environment. This also requires willingness and ability to fine-tune and blend oneself with the environment. Communication is the ability to express that attitude, conviction and technical skills in a form that can effectively reach the intended audience and persuade them to take the actions that one desires them to take. Etiquette are those commonly accepted protocols, norms and conventions that are needed to be followed to achieve effective communication.

Many organizations give training to their trainees to improve quality of work today. *Mezirow* (1991) gave Transformative learning theory of Adult learning which has the implications for developing Soft skills among prospective teachers. He defines Transformative Learning as the process by which we transform our taken for granted frames of reference including meaning perspectives, habits of mind and mind sets to make them more inclusive, discriminating, open, emotionally capable of change and reflective so that they may generate beliefs and opinions that will prove truer or justified to guide actions. Transformative Learning replaces a point of view or mind set with one that is more developed or mature. Teacher educators must foster transformative learning i.e., assist them in becoming aware, promoting critical reflection, experience in discourse and autonomous thinking. Teaching is two-way interaction between teacher and students. Various soft skills are expected within the teacher. The studies conducted by *Jody* (2005) and University of Houtown-Dautown America (2006) have clearly announced implications of soft skill training programme in teacher education.

1.1.0 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Traditionally pre-service teachers don't receive adequate soft skill training either during vocational instruction or in the class and it has been a long complaint of Principals as well as teacher educators, that the new teacher trainees do not have enough soft skills for their profession. Simply teaching to test or learning for exams is not going to help a student face everyday life situations. 21st Century Skills are key to the empowerment of Children and adolescents to deal with the issues and concerns related to their life. Teachers have a major role to play here by imparting their respective courses by using Soft Skills and at the same time making sure that their students practice Soft Skills during their school time. Therefore,

developing and enhancing the soft skills in pre-service teacher has social as well as educational significance.

Teacher is one of the main pillars of a growing and progressive society. Teachers have the responsibility of teaching as well as maximum development of students' skills and abilities. Only then students will be skilled when teachers are skilled. Obviously, the present work will give some directions to the teacher education institutions for enhancing their pre-service teachers' learning skills, literacy skills and life skills. Also, it will contribute in enrichment of new teacher education curriculum to be developed in coming years in the light of New Education Policy 2020. Such an endeavor may also effect significant change in the qualitative aspects of Teacher Education and thereby competency-based teaching will be performed by the teacher.

To be flexible and constructive in society today diversified set of skills is demanded and a broad range of attributes and temperament than ever before. Significant technological changes and developments in brain and learning research are causing a rethink of the role, content, and direction of education in schools (Bellanca & Brandt, 2010). Increased globalisation and the development of a knowledge economy (Gilbert, 2005) have led to a greater need for enhanced cultural understanding, awareness, and empathy, and consideration of a set of different skills, dispositions, and attitudes. To effectively equip with 21st century skills, specific programmes and approaches are needed and hopefully the present research will contribute to society because pre-service teachers will be socially competent when they will get training through soft skill enhancement programme. Therefore, the present research is a qualitative and innovative effort in educational and social perspectives.

2.0.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

In today's competitive world, when skill-based programs are in demand and educational system is enriching skills of students, there is need to equip teachers and prospective teachers with skills. Pacific Policy research Center (2010) also remarked in a review, "Technology is transforming how we learn and the nature of how work is conducted and the meaning of social relationships. Shared decision making, information sharing, collaboration, innovation and speed are essential in today's enterprises...much success lies in being able to communicate, share and use information to solve complex problems, in being able to adapt and innovate in response to new demands and changing circumstances, in being able to command and expand the power of technology to create

new knowledge.” Various researchers worked on strategies and initiatives to help improve professional/soft skills. *Hattie et, al.* (1996) opined that “Soft Skills” are often taken granted and recommended for soft skills mainstreaming throughout undergraduate curriculum. The level of competency in both hard and soft skills show teachers’ readiness comprehension, knowledge, and attitude. Therefore, the development of soft and hard skills should be the ultimate goal of teacher education. (Gibbs & Coffey, 2004; Fulton, 2006; Farooqi, 2013). Some earlier researches agreed that several soft skills could not be measured easily (Durowoju & Onuka, 2014).

Review of related literature shows various researches done for development of soft skills but not sufficient in field of teacher education.

Francescato et, al. (2006) focused on providing targeted online instruction for skills such as social self-efficacy. *Dharmarajan, Pachigalla and Lanka* (2012) investigated the impact of the Soft skills on the life of a student and the impact it has when he becomes a professional. Research conducted by *Greenberg and Nilssen* (2015) shows that collaboration skills and problem-solving skills are the two top soft skills on which schools should be focusing. *Buildex* (2015) suggested targeted intensive training to close the professional skills gap. *Ngang, Yunus and Hashim* (2015) studied perspective of novice teachers in Malaysia about soft skill training. Novice teachers were concerned about the insufficient soft skills acquired from teaching training in order to support them in their work place. *Kaur and Kanojia* (2016) reported that soft skills education has a significant effect on self-competence of pre-service teacher trainees. *Lavilles and Robles* (2017) found significant relation between teachers’ soft skills proficiency level and their school performance of selected schools in the division of Sultan Kudrat. *Seferoglu* (2005) found that teacher candidates were good or excellent on competency areas. Female candidates outscored males in ‘managing the instruction’ and ‘personal development.’ *Kovaces* (2019) found in his study that academic knowledge and development of theoretical knowledge appear much more emphatically with men; and the intention of getting to know the personal problems of students or the pursuit of equal opportunities with women.

Saunders and Mills (1999) defined Communication skills as the transmission of a message that involves the shared understanding between the contexts in which the communication takes place. Communication skills are important for a teacher in delivery of education to students (McCarthy and Carter, 2001). To teach in accordance with the ability and capability of the students, a teacher needs to adopt such skills of communication which motivate

the students towards their learning process (Sng Bee, 2012). Teacher with poor communication skills may cause failure of students to learn and promote their academics. Students need to understand that what is right, and what is wrong while it totally depends upon the communication skills of teachers which he adopts in class-room (Sherwyn, Osborn & Pearson, 2000). A study conducted by *Ehinder and Ajibade (2000)* indicates that for effective teaching, teacher requires good communication skills such as good communication, good classroom management, updating knowledge and maintaining personality. No one can teach effectively until having these basic skills of teaching. Different researches evolve that there is significant correlation between communication skills and supervisor perception of job performance (Maes, Weldy, & Icenogle, 1997). Teachers need clear communication for the good understanding of students and avoiding the problems for students while learning from their lecture. It is also needed by the teachers to understand first himself before teaching to students (Loss, 2000). Performance of teachers in classroom totally depends upon the communication skills. If the teacher has good communication skills, then he can easily convey his /her message or deliver the lecture in an understandable manner (Maes, Weldy & Icenogle, 1997).

A teacher needs Initiatives skill for better performance in today's life when daily changes are going on and teacher is supposed to take initiatives in school/college for different curricular, co-curricular and community-based activities. Taking initiative by students is the first step in self-directed learning which gives learners the freedom and autonomy to choose the what, why, how, and where of their learning (Francis, 2017). Recently during COVID-19 outbreak, universities and other educational institutions around the world could able to continue the teaching activities only because of teachers' initiatives skill. Teachers were not trained for any type of online teaching learning but they took initiatives for online teaching and whole time-table was followed from home in favour of students. This step of teachers made teaching-learning process that can be accessed anyplace anytime (Nedeva & Dimova, 2010). Online teaching learning made learning convenient accessible and customized. (Kimiloglu et al., 2017). When NEP 2020 is declared in July 2020, teachers took initiatives to attend webinars, conferences and faculty development programs to conceptualize it and implement it.

Teachers require technological skills as well digital skills to engage students in critical thinking and problem solving. Technology can be used to restructure and redesign the classroom to produce an environment that promotes the development of higher-order thinking skills (Kurt,

2010). *Krishnamurthy and Shettappanavar* (2019) studied the literacy of using digital resources by Female Postgraduate students as the student's level of ICT skills, frequency of internet use by the respondents, ascertain their awareness about different databases and their familiarity with various search strategies to retrieve E-resources. Google search engine is the most preferred search engine, most of the respondents i.e. 53 (68.83%) are aware of Google scholar followed by Research gate, Twitter, Slideshare, Academic.edu. and LinkedIn, SciSpace, Research ID are least used among the academic social networking sites. It is also found that there is a lack of awareness among students regarding the use of various search strategies for efficient information retrieval and only 43 (55.84%) respondents have awareness of copyrights issues. The study also highlighted the problems faced by the respondents such as poor network connectivity, access restricted by the university, which curtail the prospects of effective use of digital information resources. *Tang and Chaw* (2016) examined the relationships between effective learning and four digital literacy constructs; i.e. underpinnings, background knowledge, central competencies, and attitudes and perspectives. Data analysis showed that the four digital literacy constructs could be reduced to three, and the three digital literacy constructs each had a statistically significant relationship with the effective learning construct. It was concluded that digital literacy is a prerequisite for university students to be effective in learning in a blended learning environment. *Esteban et al.* (2023) found that teachers in primary education use strategies for data protection and digital sustainability. The teachers having more experience in teaching profession were the least likely to apply data protection protocols. Male teachers were found to promote more general data protection strategies, while female teachers were more active in the design and use of activities in the classroom.

There is lack of literature and empirical evidences about importance of leadership activities of teachers. A teacher may perceive herself as a leader when he/she is given responsibility to organize cultural activities, NCC activities, school-community interaction activities, different competitions, and other administrative responsibilities in school. *Devlin and Wickrema* (2010) identified that criteria of effective teaching in a higher educational context are like dimensions of effective leadership. *Richardson* (2003) mentions that teachers participate in school leadership to contribute to create a learning environment. They have been found to be competent, but there is no mention about their specific competencies and contributions. *Avolio, Walumbwa, and Weber* (2009) in their study concluded that leadership had been a complex and

emergent process and that was distributed and shared in organizations. They advocated for mixed methods and the context of the study was related to business establishments. It was hardly possible to draw any inference about how far their findings could help us to understand the relationship between leadership behavior of teachers in schools and their possible outcomes. Given the role of teachers as leaders of learning, there is logic in considering them as role models to their students. By acting as role models, teachers influence the morality, work ethic, citizenship, and character of their students (Lumpkin, 2008). Given that leadership is the process of influencing others, and that teaching is the process of influencing students' desire and engagement in learning, teachers are in positions of role models.

The teachers practice values, ethics and skills of professionalism, time management, punctuality, discipline, collaboration, and receptiveness to give proper results. (CBSE, Delhi, 2020). He/she is accountable for effective teaching with help of various teaching methods and innovative approaches, technology usage, interactive environment. When a teacher is held accountable for above said works, obviously her productivity is reflected in developing skills, values, personality abilities in students; maintaining the relationship with staff, parents and community members and producing quality education. Productivity of teacher has an essential and strategic role in realizing quality education. *Sultana* (2013) concluded that members' work productivity dramatically determines the success or failure of an organization. *Gilmore* (2011) states that work productivity is the power or ability of an individual to produce more creative, generative output that generates benefits. It means, accountability and productivity of teachers increase school productivity in terms of students' performance.

Collaboration is a highly effective tool for learning. Students cooperatively works together to either create projects or they can learn from each other by reading the work of their peers (Keser, Uzunboylu, & Ozdamli, 2011). Working in teams is essential for a teacher. According to *Garet et al.* (2001), teachers collaborating with each other has several advantages: working together opens opportunities to discuss problems, skills, and concepts; teachers can share common materials; teachers who share the same students can discuss student needs across classes or grade levels. Therefore, it can be said that working in groups creates a shared professional culture.

Kumar (2017) applied some activities as video analysis, newspaper analysis, case study, presentation skills etc. as soft skills considered medium to enrich English language teaching and

found positive results. *Ferranti and Rossi* (2020) used video narration to develop soft skills in initial teacher training. *Abera et al.* (2020) applied soft skill training which contributed a lot for the graduating students to have a clear understanding of the World of work. *Mozgalova et al.* (2021) highlighted the soft skills needed for future specialists in musical or artistic disciplines as well as to trace their differences with hard skills.

Mohammad et al. (2017) used E-portfolio to measure soft skills in teacher trainees and suggested to include E-portfolio assessment as integral part of traditional assessment of teacher education program. *Priya* (2011) investigated that performance in communication skill, computer skill, stress management skill, organization skill, time management skill, leadership skill, interpersonal skill and team building skill of B.Ed. students significantly influence their teaching competency. *Blessy* (2021) reported that soft skills were not significantly related with social competency of student teachers. No significant difference in soft skills with age, gender, educational qualification, and discipline.

Meor et al. (2020) assessed interpersonal skills of trainee teachers through interviews and stressed on the importance of having an assessment model to assess interpersonal skills for ESL trainee teachers. *Ahmad et al.* (2016) applied 21st century ICT literacy model among teacher trainees and found that model have good effect on ICT literacy skills on teacher trainees. *Grace Sophia and Ramesh* (2016) found that female teacher trainees were better in communication skill but no difference in mental ability and positive emotions, social skills, teacher morale, leadership skills, achievement motivation and soft skills in total. *Mishal* (2016) made an experimental study to see effectiveness of training programme on Self-efficacy of teacher trainees at B.Ed. level. *Krassen et al.* (2007) emphasized ICT teacher training for life long competence development. Keeping in view the above discussion, the investigators after reviewing the related literature on teacher education with special reference to abilities and skills required for their job success, the present study is proposed to give answers of following questions:

1. What is the status of soft skills or 21st century skills presently in pre-service teachers?
2. Whether can the soft skills be enhanced among pre-service teachers through a Soft Skill Enhancement Programme?
3. Whether the Soft Skill Enhancement Programme effect on teaching competence of future teachers?

4. Is there possibility to predict the teaching competence of Pre-service teachers on the basis of soft skill constructs.

3.0.0 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem in hand may be stated as: DEVELOPMENT AND TRY- OUT OF SOFT SKILL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME FOR PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS OF UTTAR PRADESH: ITS EFFECT ON TEACHING COMPETENCE

3.1.0 OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF THE KEY TERMS

The key terms used in the present research, namely are briefly clarified as follows:

1. Soft Skills: Soft skills are taken in terms of 21st century skills as given by CBSE in “21st Century Skills: A Handbook”. These are defined operationally as given in following table:

Table 2: Definition of Soft Skills Dimensions

SN	Group of Soft Skills	Name of Soft Skills	Definition of the Specific soft skills
1	Learning Skills (4Cs)	Critical thinking Skills	The capability of objective analysis of information and reach a right conclusion.
		Creativity and Innovation	Creativity skills refers to new ways of seeing or doing things and includes four components: fluency (generating new ideas), flexibility (shifting perspective easily), originality (conceiving of something new), and elaboration (building on others' ideas). Innovative Skills mean skills for thinking creatively to develop something new/ unique / improved / distinctive.
		Collaboration Skills	Ability to effectively work together with others. This skill involves working together while taking actions respecting others' needs and perspectives, contributing to and accepting others, develop interest and fun in the work, helps a person to understand social and environmental concerns better.
		Communication Skills	Ability to express one's opinions, desires, needs, apprehensions etc. oneself appropriately, verbally and non-verbally.
2	Literacy Skills (IMT skills)	Information Literacy Skills	Ability to access information (traditional or digital), manage the flow of information, to understand and critically evaluate different aspects of content and information and awareness of ethical and legal issues surrounding the access and use of information

		Media Literacy Skills	Ability to understand the preparation and purpose of media messages, Examine various manners/ ways of interpreting messages, understand the ethical/legal issues regarding the access and use of media and understand and utilize the most appropriate media creation tools, characteristics and conventions
		Technology Literacy Skills	Ability to use technology as a tool to research, organize, evaluate and communication information and use digital technologies, communication networks, and tools to access, manage, integrate, evaluate and create information for functioning for class
3	Life Skills (FLIPS)	Flexibility and Adaptability	Flexibility refers to a person's ability to change his actions and steps taken by him according to a new situation, and efficiently facing an unprecedented situation, without compromising on ethics and values. Adaptability is creating modifications or changes in oneself to suit the new environment and find the best possible solution to go forward despite adverse conditions.
		Leadership and Responsibility	Leadership is the ability to lead a team and be capable of effective team management in relation to real world challenges. Being Responsible means being a good and effective/ sensitive citizen. Be aware of the important social and national issues that may have an impact on our daily lives, be aware of our fundamental duties and rights and embed the core democratic values of India and strive to live by them.
		Initiative and Self Direction	Initiation skill involves the ability to begin a task independently. It helps the individual to build his/her own path of development. Self-direction is a skill to work with integrity on self-motivation and taking initiatives.
		Productivity and Accountability	Productivity in any individual can be understood as fulfilment of any task within a given time-period. Accountability can be understood as feeling responsible for any task done.
		Social and Cross-Cultural Interaction	These are the skills to communicate, work collaboratively and effectively in diverse social and cultural environments.

2. Soft Skill Enhancement Programme: Soft Skill Enhancement programme is the programme developed by researcher to develop soft skills in pre-service teachers. The programme includes theoretical content online training, presentations, activities.

3. Pre-Service Teachers: Pre-service teachers are the students studying in B.Ed. I class in colleges of Uttar Pradesh

4. Teaching Competence: Teaching competence is the competency of teacher in areas as It includes knowledge of subject, lesson planning, classroom management, development of teaching-learning material, evaluation, interpersonal relations, time management, relations with parents, community, and other agencies.

3.2.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

The main objective of the project is to develop a Soft Skill Enhancement Programme and try out of the programme on pre-service teachers and its impact on teaching competence. In order to achieve the main objective, following sub-objectives are determined:

1. To assess the status of soft skills in pre-service teachers.
2. To develop and try out of the Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on pre-service teachers.
3. To study the effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Teaching competence of pre-service teachers.
4. To study the effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Teaching competence of Preservice Teachers with reference to their subject stream.
5. To study the effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Teaching competence of Preservice Teachers with reference to Self-Efficacy.
6. To study the effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on specific Soft Skills of pre-service teachers.
7. To study the correlation in Soft Skills and Teaching competence of Preservice Teachers.
8. To find the predictor variables of Teaching competence among the selected components of Soft Skills.

3.3.0 HYPOTHESES OF THE RESEARCH

Main hypotheses to be tested and verified are stated as under:

- H1.0 There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Teaching competence of Pre-service teachers.

- H2.0 There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group and Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to subject stream.
- H2.1 There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group of Pre-service teachers with reference to subject stream.
- H2.2 There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to subject stream.
- H3.0 There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group and Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy.
- H3.1 There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group of Pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy.
- H3.2 There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy.
- H4.0 There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on specific Soft Skills of Preservice Teachers.
- H4.1. There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Collaboration skills of Preservice Teachers.
- H4.2. There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Communication skills of Preservice Teachers.
- H4.3. There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Information literacy skills of Preservice Teachers.
- H4.4 There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Media literacy skills of Preservice Teachers.
- H4.5 There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Technology literacy skills of Preservice Teachers.
- H5.0 There is no significant correlation in Soft Skills and Teaching competence of Pre-service Teachers.

H6.0 There is no significant difference in the contribution of Soft Skills, Emotional intelligence, and Self-efficacy in Teaching competence of Pre service Teachers.

4.0.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To arrive the solution of the problem in hand, specific research method, design, sampling technique and tools are used which are described in succeeding pages:

4.1.0 RESEARCH METHOD

The Experimental Method was adopted for study. In this method, Experimentation helps in establishing causal relationships among different variables under controlled conditions. In this method, researcher studies the effect of independent variable on dependent variable following the steps: Control, manipulation, observation, and retention. In this study, an attempt was made to study effectiveness of Soft Skill Enhancement programme and its effect on teaching competence of pre-service teachers in controlled conditions. Therefore, Soft Skill Enhancement programme as treatment acts as independent variable and teaching competence and soft skills were considered as dependent variable.

4.2.0 RESEARCH DESIGN

Researchers used Pre-test Post-test Control Group Design. This design is also called as 'Randomized Control-group Pre-test-Post-test Design'. In pursuance of the objective, two equated groups were formed by randomly assigning subjects to the groups. Both groups were administered a Teaching Competence scale and Soft Skill Inventory as pre-tests. The treatment in form of Soft Skill Enhancement Program is given to Experimental group. The duration of the treatment has been similar. At the end of the treatment, both groups were administered the same Teaching Competence scale and Soft Skill Inventory. In this design, the dependent variables (Teaching competency and Soft skills) have been measured before (pre-test) and after (post-test) the treatment (Soft Skill Enhancement Program) in the randomized equivalent groups. The difference between means of pre-test and post-test is found in order to ascertain whether the Soft Skill Enhancement Program produced a significant effect.

Following table describes the research design of the study:

Table 3: Research Design of the Study

Phase 1: Selection of Variables	<p>Selection of Variables taken in the study</p> <p>a. Independent variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soft Skill Enhancement Programme and Conventional training <p>b. Dependent Variables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Soft Skills of Pre-service Teachers in terms of Learning Skills, Literacy Skills and Life Skills ➤ Teaching competence in terms of academic, professional and personal competence <p>c. Control variables</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Gender ➤ Age ➤ Emotional Intelligence <p>d. Intervening variables</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Subject stream ➤ Self Efficacy
Phase Two: Preparation of tools	Preparation of the Soft Skills (21 st century Skill) Inventory
Phase Three: Selection of Sample	Selection of sample for the study and random assignment of Pre-service Teachers into Control and Experimental group after matching on Emotional Intelligence.
Phase Four: Pre-testing of the variables	<p>Administration of the tools before treatment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Self Efficacy b. Soft Skill Inventory c. Teaching Competence Test
Phase Five: Preparation of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme	Preparation of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme for 21 st century skills and try out on Pre-service Teachers
Phase Six: Post Treatment measurement of variables	<p>Administration of the tools after treatment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Soft Skill Inventory b. Teaching Competence Test

4.3.0 VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

In research, variables are the conditions or characteristics which can be controlled, observed or manipulated. Following variables are studied in the present study:

1. **Independent Variables:** An independent variable being independent in nature vary independently and its variation effect is observed on dependent variable. There are both type of training programmes in study: Conventional training and Soft Skill Enhancement Programme. Pre-service teachers at secondary level in Uttar Pradesh undergo two year

training in which theory and practical knowledge is given through seven core courses, six pedagogical courses and six EPC courses.

During the first year, in Pedagogical courses, B.Ed. offers the training amounting to a minimum of 5 weeks which includes: One week workshop on Lesson-Planning based on constructivist approach, One week workshop on 'Micro-Teaching', One week Practice-Teaching in Simulated condition in each Pedagogy course and Two week Practice-Teaching in Real-Class room situation in a school. In present study, 3 weeks training of lesson planning, microteaching and practice teaching in simulated conditions were termed as "Conventional teacher training". This training was given to both groups.

Soft Skill Enhancement Programme was developed by the researchers and programme was provided to Pre-service teachers online. The programme contains all theory, practical sessions, and assignments. This program's duration was decided as 40 hours in which orientation with programme, exploring the skills, applying the skills, and reflecting on program were the main components of the programme. This training programme was given to experimental group only. Therefore, following were the independent variables in study:

- i. Soft Skill Enhancement Programme
- ii. Conventional Programme

2. **Dependent variables:** The dependent variables are the characteristics which can be changed as independent variable varies.

- i. **Soft Skills:** In the present study, Soft Skills are measured by self-constructed inventory in which a combined set of different skills as; Critical thinking, Creativity and Innovation, Collaboration, Communication, Information literacy, Media literacy, Technological literacy, Flexibility and Adaptability, Leadership and Responsibility, Initiative and Self-direction, Productivity and Accountability, Social and Cross-cultural interaction was selected.

- ii. **Teaching Competence:** Teaching effectiveness depends directly on Teaching competence and many researches indicate that teaching competence is the important factor which is responsible for good teaching learning process. Therefore, it is considered as dependent variable in study.

3. **Extraneous (Controlled) variables:** These variables make effects on dependent variables and to ascertain the effectiveness of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Pre-service teachers' Soft skills and Teaching competency, three variables were considered as control variables:

i. Gender: There are numerous factors which affect teaching competency. Research literature shows that students are little biased to female teachers (Feldman, 1993). *Sadi* (2005) observed that gender is one of the factors affecting teaching competency. Therefore, controlling gender variable, only female pre-service teachers were included.

ii. Age: It is considered that age may be a factor which affects teacher competency in digital sustainability which is the most important soft skill these days. So, age was controlled in present research and only pre-service teachers in age range of 20-25 years were selected in sample.

iii. Emotional intelligence: Many studies point out that Emotional intelligence plays important and significant role in pre-service teacher's teaching effectiveness as well as teaching competency. (Bansibihari and Surwade, 2008; Adeyemo, Agokei and Chukwudi, 2014). Hence, researcher controlled Emotional intelligence of pre-service teachers by matching groups on Emotional intelligence through randomization.

iv. Teacher Effect: Students' performance and achievement are affected by Teacher effect, therefore this is controlled by training both the groups Experimental as well as control group by teacher educators of same educational qualification and teaching experience.

4. **Intervening Variables:** The variables which have an impact on the dependent variable even before the application of the treatment but are not controlled by researcher due to some reasons. In present study, following variables are taken as intervening variables:

i. Subject stream

ii. Self-Efficacy

4.3.1 CONTROL OF VARIABLES

In experimental researches, control of variable is important factor. To study the effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Pre-service teachers, three variables as gender, age and

emotional intelligence were directly controlled. All units selected for study were females having age of 20-25 years. The ‘Teacher Effect’ on training strategies followed to train Pre-service Teachers of Control and Experimental group was controlled by training both the groups by Teacher Educators with same Educational Qualification and number of years of Teaching Experience. The educational qualification of the Pre-service Teachers belonging to Control group and Experimental group was same and all 200 Pre-service Teachers were in B.Ed. I. Thus, the effect of extraneous variables – Teacher Effect, educational qualification, age, and gender of the Pre-service Teachers on effectiveness of training strategies was also controlled.

4.3.2 MATCHING EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUP

Control and experimental group were matched on emotional intelligence. Before trying out the Soft Skill Enhancement Programme, emotional intelligence test was administered on all Pre-service teachers (N=200). The scores gained by pre-service teachers were arranged in order and each alternate sample unit was assigned to experimental group and control group. In this way effect of Emotional intelligence was also controlled in study.

4.4.0 SAMPLING OF RESPONDENTS

- a) **Population:** All the pre-service teachers studying in B.Ed. Colleges in Uttar Pradesh (West).
- b) **Sampling Size:** 200 teacher trainees.
- c) **Sampling selection procedure:** A list of colleges offering B.Ed. affiliated to C.C.S. University, Meerut was downloaded through university website assuming proper representation of B.Ed. colleges of West Uttar Pradesh region. For selection of colleges, Random sampling technique was employed and 4 colleges were selected considering the maximum intake of pre-service teachers in one unit as 55. These selected colleges were visited by researcher keeping in view the availability of students in college for data collection and treatment. Then all pre-service teachers were considered in sampling frame, then 200 pre-service teachers were selected through random cluster random sampling technique. All female pre-service teachers in age range of 20-25 years were given Emotional Intelligence Scale. Scores obtained on Emotional Intelligence Scale

were arranged in ascending order and each alternate pre-service teacher as sample unit was assigned to Control group and Experimental group. Sample design is given in fig. 2.

Fig.1: Flow Chart for Sample Selection

4.5.0 TOOLS USED IN RESEARCH

It is very important to select appropriate tools for good research. Keeping the objectives of the study in mind, investigators selected appropriate tools and relevance, availability, suitability of administration, reliability and validity were taken care of. Following tools were used to conduct the research:

Table 4: Tools used in the Study

SN	Name of Variable	Tool	Developed by	Purpose of use
1	Soft Skills	Soft Skill Inventory	Self-constructed	To measure soft skills (Pre-test, Post-test)
2	Emotional Intelligence	Emotional Intelligence Test	Zainuddin, R. (2014)	To test Emotional Intelligence and matching the groups
3	Teaching Competence	Teaching Competence Scale	Vidushy, V. & N. Kishore (2021)	To measure Teaching competence
4	Teacher's Self Efficacy	Teacher's Self Efficacy Scale	Ansari, Khan & Khan (2017)	To measure Self-efficacy

4.5.1 SOFT SKILL INVENTORY

Soft Skill Inventory was constructed by investigators themselves by which the Soft Skill as a psychoeducational construct can be measured in the manner which research aimed. Considering the nature of research problem and population for which the inventory was constructed, all steps of construction of tools were followed given as under:

1. **Planning:** All Soft skills taken in study were further explored with help of reviewing the related literature, talks with colleagues and available tools to measure soft skills. For this purpose, psychological tools named as Critical Thinking Scale by Murthy (2015); Interpersonal Skills Inventory constructed by Jakubowska, Sharma and Nigam (2018); Study Skill Assessment Tool by Vijaybanu (2017); Self Confidence Inventory designed by Gupta (2013); Teacher Self Concept Scale constructed by Sharma and & Maurya (2017); Self-concept cum Rating Scale developed by Saraswat (2011); Teachers’ Professional Development Scale by Bhutia (2014) ; Teacher Behaviour Scale by Rani and Tyagi (2015); Teachers organizational commitment by Jamal and Rahman (2014); Teaching Style Scale by Sharma and Saran (2017); PGT Quality of Life Scale by Verma (1998) were thoroughly studied to take insight for constructing the items and specific behaviours to be considered in the specific soft skills.

Construction of inventory was started with preparation of blue print deciding the specific behaviours for all skills and length of the test, type and nature of test-items and scoring method of the tool. Considering the nature of soft skills taken, type of test-items was decided. For Learning skills and Literacy skills (cognitive in nature) as critical thinking, creativity and innovation, collaboration, communication; information literacy, media literacy and technology literacy, items as multiple-choice, open, and 5 point rating scale type items were constructed while on life skills (non-cognitive in nature) as flexibility and adaptability, leadership and responsibility, initiativeness and self-direction, productivity and accountability, social and cross-cultural interaction (FLIPS), all items on rating scale were constructed. Blue print of the Inventory is given under:

Table 5: Blue Print of Soft Skill Inventory

SN	Skills	Dimensions	No. of Items	Weightage
1	Critical Thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Use reasoning appropriate to the situation• Analyze and evaluate various perspectives	8	5%

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making correlation between various types of information available • Analyze and Interpret the available information and form conclusions, Reflect the pros and cons of experience to solve problem 		
2	Creativity and Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use various techniques for creating an evolving new ideas • Original and Innovative ideas • Elaborate, refine, analyze and evaluate ideas to improve one's own creative efforts • Be open and flexibility for responsive to diversity • treat failure as an opportunity to learn and improve 	18	11%
3	Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to work effectively and respectfully • Be adaptable to accomplish a common goal • Assume shared responsibility for collaborative work • value the individual contributions made by each team member 	17	10%
4	Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verbal communication • Non-verbal communication • Visual communication • Written communication 	14	8%
5	Information Literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiently and critically access and evaluation of information • Manage the flow of information from a wide variety of sources • Apply a fundamental understanding of the ethical/legal issues surrounding the access and use of information 	12	7%
6	Media Literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the preparation and purpose of media messages • Examine various manners/ ways of interpreting messages • Understand the ethical/legal issues regarding the access and use of media • Understand and utilize the most appropriate media creation tools, characteristics, and conventions 	15	9%
7	Technology Literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use technology as a tool to research, organize, evaluate and communication information • Use digital technologies, communication networks, and tools to access, manage, integrate, evaluate and create information for functioning for class 	14	8%
8	Flexibility and Adaptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt to varied and multiple roles, jobs responsibilities, schedules and context • Work effectively in scenarios of changing priorities • Incorporate feedback effectively • Deal positively with praise, setbacks and criticism • Understand, negotiate and balance diverse views and beliefs to get solutions, particularly in multi-cultural environments 	14	8%
9	Leadership and Responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use interpersonal and problem –solving skills to influence and guide others towards a goal • Involve strengths of others to accomplish a common goal 	15	9%

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspire others to attain their best by example • Demonstrate integrity and ethical behavior in using influence and power • Act responsibly keeping in mind the welfare of society and nation 		
10	Initiative and Self - Direction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set goals with tangible and intangible success criteria • Utilize time and manage workload efficiently • Monitor, define, prioritize and complete your tasks • Explore new information to achieve mastery in a task • Take initiative to get skills up to the professional level • Be a life- long learner • Critically and positively analyze past to make the future better 	13	8%
11	Productivity and Accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set and meet goals, even in the face of obstacles and competing pressures • Prioritize, plan and manage work to achieve the intended result • Practice values, ethics and skills of professionalism, time management, punctuality, discipline, patience, collaboration, and receptiveness to give proper results 	16	9%
12	Social and Cross – Cultural Interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active listening • Know when to speak • Behave respectfully • Respect differences and work effectively with people from diverse backgrounds • Be open to various perspectives • Blend and use ideas from diverse teams to innovate and implement 	14	8%
		Total	170	

2. Initial Draft: Then items were pooled based on the prepared blue print and the initial draft of inventory consisted 170 items. Type of items and no. of items are shown in following table:

Table 6: Skills, Type of Items and Number of Items

SN	Skills	Types of Items			Total Items
		MCQ	Open	Rating	
1	Critical Thinking	6	2	-	8
2	Creativity and Innovation	-	4	14	18
3	Collaboration	-	2	15	17
4	Communication	-	-	14	14
5	Information Literacy	-	10	2	12
6	Media Literacy	-	2	13	15
7	Technology Literacy	4	6	4	14
8	Flexibility and Adaptability	-	-	14	14
9	Leadership and Responsibility	-	-	15	15

10	Initiative and Self-direction	-	-	13	13
11	Productivity and Accountability	-	-	16	16
12	Social and Cross-cultural Interaction	-	-	14	14
	TOTAL				170

Investigators tried out this first draft of inventory on small group of subjects (10 pre-service teachers) from the population to take a rough idea of the difficulty of items and understanding of items. Also this draft was get checked by an English language expert. Then, the items were edited and modified keeping in mind all the things as language as suggested by expert, questions attempted by the subjects, duplication of the sense of item, and the type of response given by pre-service teachers and 31 items were shortened in Inventory.

3. Second Draft: Now second draft having 139 items was prepared for subject and research expert opinion. For this purpose, Inventory was prepared in googleform (<https://rb.gy/gh1w84>) for expert opinion on three point scale: Important, Needs Improvement and Unimportant. At the end of every question, space is also given for their open suggestions and 10 experts gave their individual opinion. Their responses were analysed and the items pointed by them as “Unimportant” were discarded from the tool and few items were modified. Investigators discussed the items of tool telephonically also whenever discussion required. In this way, a new draft was prepared. After making modifications as per suggested by experts, total items in new draft were remained as 126. It was also suggested to keep the scoring pattern same for at least dimension of the tool. Therefore, some dimensions were measured based on rating scale only and some were measured on multiple choice-based questions and open questions. This draft was then processed for item analysis.

4. Item analysis: It is the process of item validation. The draft consisting 126 items was allowed to the process of item analysis. For this purpose, this draft of the tool was administered on 60 pre-service teachers (B.Ed. I students). Because of the nature of the tool having three types of items and availability of computer facilities, discrimination power of the items is to compute the correlation of each item with the total score. One advantage of this method is that items may be scored right/wrong, or scores may be awarded on degree of correctness when certain complex item formats are used or when there is a bonus for rapid

responding. (Both of these scoring procedures are used on the Weschler scales, for example, although the instrument is not formally an objective test). The item-total correlation uses all the data rather than just the extreme cases and the resulting correlations have the same general properties as the D-index.

The items with the highest values (over 0.50) were retained; the items having lowest values (below 0.20) were eliminated and the items between these two points were considered for modification. Items with negative discriminative values were rejected. Following tables reflects item-total correlation values of all items of the Inventory:

Table 7: Item Total Correlation Values of all items of SSI

Part	Skills	Item no.	Correlation value (r)	Remark	Total item remained
1	Critical Thinking	1	0.509553	Accepted	07
		2	0.075966	Accepted	
		3	-0.02576	Rejected	
		4	0.643285	Accepted	
		5	0.670419	Accepted	
		6	0.499419	Accepted	
		7	Open Question	Accepted	
		8	Open Question	Accepted	
2	Creativity and Innovation	1	0.560517	Accepted	12
		2	0.570799	Accepted	
		3	0.452691	Accepted	
		4	0.556508	Accepted	
		5	0.562225	Accepted	
		6	0.650082	Accepted	
		7	0.463789	Accepted	
		8	0.519115	Accepted	
		9	0.483526	Accepted	
		10	0.507217	Accepted	
		11	Open Question	Accepted	
		12	Open Question	Accepted	
3	Collaboration	1	0.578326	Accepted	10
		2	0.629194	Accepted	
		3	0.502307	Accepted	
		4	0.485566	Accepted	
		5	0.490591	Accepted	
		6	0.543005	Accepted	
		7	0.572632	Accepted	
		8	0.469928	Accepted	
		9	0.500551	Accepted	
		10	-0.05794	Rejected	
		11	0.561517	Accepted	
4	Communication	1	0.548743	Accepted	10
		2	0.522047	Accepted	
		3	0.555328	Accepted	
		4	0.490763	Accepted	

		5	0.553708	Accepted	
		6	0.666481	Accepted	
		7	-0.30819	Rejected	
		8	0.594692	Accepted	
		9	0.392319	Accepted	
		10	0.537101	Accepted	
		11	Open question	Accepted	
5	Information Literacy	1	0.519329	Accepted	08
		2	0.711748	Accepted	
		3	0.539962	Accepted	
		4	0.570511	Accepted	
		5	0.513289	Accepted	
		6	0.713659	Accepted	
		7	0.644595	Accepted	
		8	0.719783	Accepted	
6	Media Literacy	1	0.486873	Accepted	10
		2	-0.09143	Rejected	
		3	0.141107	Rejected	
		4	0.324738	Accepted	
		5	0.647221	Accepted	
		6	0.652924	Accepted	
		7	0.705218	Accepted	
		8	0.627166	Accepted	
		9	0.646509	Accepted	
		10	0.658252	Accepted	
		11	Open question	Accepted	
		12	Open question	Accepted	
7	Technology Literacy	1	0.666167	Accepted	10
		2	0.834614	Accepted	
		3	0.861472	Accepted	
		4	0.556381	Accepted	
		5	0.68848	Accepted	
		6	-0.08141	Rejected	
		7	0.722921	Accepted	
		8	0.726412	Accepted	
		9	0.680059	Accepted	
		10	0.593226	Accepted	
		11	Open question	Accepted	
8	Flexibility and Adaptability	1	0.545112	Accepted	09
		2	0.506127	Accepted	
		3	0.677358	Accepted	
		4	0.585571	Accepted	
		5	0.710615	Accepted	
		6	0.627285	Accepted	
		7	0.644667	Accepted	
		8	0.676649	Accepted	
		9	0.540527	Accepted	
9	Leadership Responsibility and	1	0.466602	Accepted	09
		2	0.687708	Accepted	
		3	0.599082	Accepted	
		4	0.550442	Rejected	
		5	0.776708	Accepted	

		6	0.531422	Accepted	
		7	0.724438	Accepted	
		8	0.636359	Accepted	
		9	0.459981	Accepted	
		10	0.523321	Accepted	
10	Initiative and Self - Direction	1	0.492932	Accepted	11
		2	0.578529	Accepted	
		3	0.621207	Accepted	
		4	0.656402	Accepted	
		5	0.513218	Accepted	
		6	-0.06784	Rejected	
		7	0.597297	Accepted	
		8	0.488323	Accepted	
		9	0.460104	Accepted	
		10	0.485764	Accepted	
		11	0.647836	Accepted	
		12	0.681273	Accepted	
11	Productivity and Accountability	1	0.573004	Accepted	11
		2	0.694839	Accepted	
		3	0.688412	Accepted	
		4	0.595652	Accepted	
		5	0.380112	Accepted	
		6	0.608022	Accepted	
		7	0.538712	Accepted	
		8	0.458107	Accepted	
		9	0.410032	Accepted	
		10	0.635728	Accepted	
		11	0.593226	Accepted	
12	Social and Cross-cultural Interaction	1	0.435112	Accepted	11
		2	0.660018	Accepted	
		3	0.619616	Accepted	
		4	0.502379	Accepted	
		5	0.614717	Accepted	
		6	0.617323	Accepted	
		7	0.558088	Accepted	
		8	0.605761	Accepted	
		9	0.649449	Accepted	
		10	0.526297	Accepted	
		11	0.568542	Accepted	
	Total Items	126			118

Therefore, the Soft Skill Inventory consists of 118 items. Few items are performance based and few are perception based. Rating type items were provided 5 points as Very often, often, sometimes, rarely and not at all. Pre-service teachers took approximately 1hour 30 minutes to complete it. (Appendix-1.1)

5. Reliability: The reliability of the scale was calculated through Test-retest Method. The test was administered on 50 pre-service teachers at the interval of approx. 40 days. The value of reliability coefficient was found to be 0.79, which is fairly satisfactory.
6. Validity: The test was given to 10 experts (research and language). They were requested to give their suggestions on googleform. Their suggestions and approval for each item were thoroughly studied and modifications were done in the items as suggested by experts. In this way, content validity of the Inventory was established.
7. Scoring: Soft Skill inventory has variety of questions, therefore scoring key was developed as per requirement of item. The possible minimum score on inventory is 88 and maximum possible score is 520. (Appendix1.2)

4.5.2 TEACHER'S TEACHING COMPETENCE SCALE

Teacher's Teaching Competence Scale constructed by Vidushy, V. and N. Kishor (2021) was used to test teaching competence. The teaching competence scale is Likert type scale which consists of 35 items. Items are related to planning lessons, classroom management, knowledge of subject, interpersonal relationship, development of teaching learning material, time management, evaluation process during teaching learning, competencies related to working with parents, community, and other agencies. The test is group administered and verbal in nature. Test can be administered in group and can be completed in 20-25 minutes. The scoring of the scale is based on the method of summated ratings i.e., each item was rated on five consecutive point that if the answer to a positive item means Most of the time, the score is 5, to often, the score is 4, rarely the score is 3, for sometimes option, the score is 2 and for Not at all, the score is 1. Maximum possible score is 175 and minimum score is 35. Reliability of test was calculated as 0.95 with help of test-retest method. Internal reliability coefficients of the scale and its dimensions were also calculated and found satisfactory. Content validity of the tool was established with help of experts of the field as well as language. (Appendix-2)

4.5.3 EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE TEST

The test constructed by Zainuddin, R. (2014) was used to test Emotional Intelligence of pre-service teachers. The test has 30 items based on five dimensions: self-awareness, self-

regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. The test was of rating scale type and the responses were judged on 3 point scale. This test can be used in group as well as for individual assessment. It is self-administering in nature. Reliability of the test was determined by calculating Cronbach's alpha coefficient which was found as 0.70 fairly high and acceptable. Concurrent validity for the test was calculated as 0.28 which is significant at 0.05 level. (Appendix-3)

4.5.4 TEACHER'S SELF EFFICACY SCALE

Teacher's Self Efficacy Scale constructed by Ansari, Khan and Khan (2017) was applied in study. Self Efficacy was measured by six dimensions as restraint, outgoing, evolving, versatile, high expectations, constructive. Total 23 items were included in the test and items were prepared with Likert type 6 responses- Strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat disagree, somewhat agree, agree, and strongly agree. The scale can be administered on an individual or on a group. Reliability coefficient of the scale was calculated through Cronbach alpha method and found 0.849. The internal consistency of the scale is quite high and the scale is highly reliable. Face validity of the scale was verified by number of experts. The minimum possible score of the scale was 23 and maximum score was 138.

All above three tools were suitable for pre-service teachers; language of the tools is simple and clear; tools were easy to administer; also used in various research work in different universities and colleges. (Appendix-4)

4.6.0 DEVELOPMENT OF SOFT SKILL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME

The main objective of the present study was to develop a Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on selected Soft Skills and to study its effect on Soft Skills and Teaching competency of Pre-service Teachers. Teachers use many soft skills during teaching-learning process and school activities. Soft skills are skills broadly applied across all the disciplines in school (Matteson, Anderson, & Boyden, 2016). Soft skills really make teacher competent academically, personally and professionally. For development of programme, many training programmes and modules on soft skills were reviewed. Overview of the programmes shows that online and offline both types of programmes are being developed for skill development. Following steps were followed in

development of programme:

1. **Planning:** To develop Soft Skill Enhancement Programme, investigators worked upon following points:

- i. Deciding soft skills on which programme is to developed: To select soft skills to be included in programme, Self-constructed Soft Skill inventory was administered on pre-service teachers and five skills were selected based on performance of pre-service teachers. Therefore, the skills selected for developing the programme were: Communication Skill, Collaboration Skill, Information Literacy Skill, Media literacy Skill and Technology Literacy Skill. Pre-service teachers did not exhibit good performance on these skills.
- ii. Objectives of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme: Following objectives were decided: After training program, B.Ed. students will be able to:
 - Work effectively and respectfully in team.
 - Adapt to accomplish a common goal.
 - Assume shared responsibility for collaborative work.
 - Value the individual contributions made by each team member.
 - Use collaborative methods in class.
 - Verbally communicate effectively in class.
 - Communicate in class keeping in mind non-verbal communication
 - Use visuals effectively in teaching learning process.
 - Write email to School Principal efficiently.
 - Write speech in any school program as Cultural program or any intercollegiate Sports meet, or Academic program.
 - Talk with Parents keeping in mind students' Psychology
 - Efficiently and critically access and evaluate information
 - Manage the flow of information from a wide variety of sources
 - Apply a fundamental understanding of the ethical/ legal issues surrounding the access and use of information
 - Understand the preparation and purpose of media messages
 - Examine various manners/ ways of interpreting messages
 - Understand the ethical/legal issues regarding the access and use of media
 - Understand and utilize the most appropriate media creation tools, characteristics and conventions
 - Use technology as a tool to research, organize, evaluate and communication information

- Use digital technologies, communication networks, and tools to access, manage, integrate, evaluate and create information for functioning for class
- iii. Mode of Programme: To decide the mode of programme, investigators made discussion with different college teachers and pre-service teachers. Keeping the availability of pre-service teachers for attending programme, online mode was adopted by which college assignments and classes will not be suffered. All online sessions were scheduled in evening time.
- iv. Structure and duration of the Programme: Soft Skill Enhancement programme was divided into four phases: Orientation, Explore, Apply and Reflect and duration decided was 40 hours.
- a. Orientation- It was decided to orient pre-service teachers with all soft skills used in teaching-learning process, their importance for a teacher and all sessions to be conducted during the programme, activities to be conducted during the programme and assessment process. The orientation was conducted for 3 hours.
- b. Explore: In this phase, pre-service teachers were given opportunity to explore all five skills with help of online workshop and module provided. Time of 30 hours was allotted to five skills. Eminent subject experts in the field trained them in skills and shared their experiences during Online workshops.
- i. Communication- 6 hrs. (3 hrs. Theory and 3 hrs. online workshop)
 - ii. Collaboration – 6 hrs. (3 hrs. Theory and 3 hrs. online workshop)
 - iii. Information Literacy-6 hrs. (3 hrs. Theory and 3 hrs. online workshop)
 - iv. Media Literacy- 6 hrs. (3 hrs. Theory and 3 hrs. online workshop)
 - v. Technology Literacy- 6 hrs. (3 hrs. Theory and 3 hrs. online workshop)
- c. Apply: In this phase, pre-service teachers applied their knowledge in activities and assignments given during online sessions. Pre-service teachers individually conducted the activities and submitted their assignments. Pre-service teachers were also given post-test as Soft Skill Inventory to get their performance after attending programme. This whole process was given as 5 hrs..
- d. Reflect: Reflection is the important part of the programme. All pre-service teachers were instructed to give their reflections about the Soft Skill Enhancement programme. Duration of this phase was 2 hrs.

2. **Preparation of Modules:** 5 modules were drafted including instructional objectives, content, important links and references for further reading. Modules were prepared to give theoretical knowledge of the skills and practical experiences with activities were done in online sessions.
3. **Validation of the Programme:** The draft of the Training Programme on selected Soft Skills was given to the subject as well as research experts. Their comments on the programme were as:
 - Selection of soft skills adequately
 - Inclusion of comprehensive content in modules
 - Programme may include presentations individually by pre-service teachers exhibiting all the soft skills included.
4. **Final Draft of the Programme:** The suggestions given by experts were incorporated and the complete Programme on selected Soft Skills was made ready for field try out. (Appendix-5)

4.7.0 DATA COLLECTION AND ORGANIZATION

The study employed a quantitative methodology of data collection. The investigators made contacts with higher authority of the colleges which were selected in sample. After getting the permission of authority, data collection was undertaken in three stages:

1. Pre-treatment stage: Before applying the Soft Skill Enhancement programme, data related to following variables was collected:

- i. Soft Skills: To assess soft skills of pre-service teachers, Self-constructed Soft Skill inventory consisting 12 dimensions and 118 items was administered on 200 pre-service teachers and face to face instructions were given to all. This inventory takes time to fill, therefore investigators paid personal attention for completion and accuracy. Scores obtained on selected 5 skills as Communication skill, Collaboration skill, Information literacy skill, Media literacy skill and Technology literacy skill were also considered as pre-test scores on soft skills.
- ii. Teaching Competency: To measure teaching competency, Teaching competency scale constructed by Vidushy, V. and N. Kishor (2021) was administered on 200 pre-service teachers. This is dependent variable; therefore, its scores were also considered as pre-test scores.

Researcher tried to give comfortable environment to pre-service teachers for completing teaching competency scale.

iii. Self-Efficacy: Self efficacy was considered as intervening variable in present study. For this purpose, Teacher's Self Efficacy Scale constructed by Ansari, Khan and Khan (2017) was administered on all 200 pre-service teachers. Personal attention was given to all pre-service teachers. Then all tests were collected.

iv. Emotional Intelligence: Emotional intelligence was considered as control variable. Emotional Intelligence Test constructed by Zainuddin, R. (2014) was administered on 200 pre-service teachers. Based on obtained scores, control and experimental group were matched to avoid the difference of Emotional intelligence on treatment and two groups as control and experimental were made of 100 each.

2. Treatment stage: In consultation with Principals of selected colleges for sample, it was planned to apply treatment in the form of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme to Experimental group of pre-service teachers (N=100) for a period of total 40 hours including theory modules and online sessions. Module was given in form of e-content (Word file or powerpoint file). Online sessions were conducted in evening for 1 hour 30 minutes for 21 days considering the daily time table of B.Ed. students. In these sessions, eminent subject experts gave clarifications about soft skills, shared their experiences, made discussions, and gave opportunities to develop and exhibit their skills. Assignments and presentations were also assigned to pre-service teachers. The Pre-service Teachers of the Control group (N=100) were subjected to Conventional Training programme regarding soft skills and skills in teaching competency. It was provided by the Teacher Educators of the Colleges.

3. Post-treatment stage: In this stage of the study, data for all dependent variables of the study was collected. After applying the treatment, googleform of Soft Skill Inventory having five selected skills and Teaching competency were prepared and pre-service teachers were asked to fill it and data related to these variables was collected.

After collection of the data, scoring of all response sheets was done and all the data was entered in MS Excel.

4.8.0 LITERATURE CONTROL

The data have subsequently also been confirmed by a literature control. Though very few researches in Indian context were found, the results of this research study were compared with the results of other researches previously undertaken around this topic in order to determine differences, similarities, gaps and unique contributions. (Poggenpoel, 1993).

4.9.0 ETHICAL MEASURES

The researcher has the responsibility to protect the participants throughout a research study (Cresswell, 1994). For the purpose of this study the following ethical measures were adhered to; confidentiality, anonymity, and full disclosure of information about the research (Kvale, 1996).

5.0.0 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The study employed quantitative methodology of data analysis. Analysis of the data was done in direction of objectives and hypothesis testing using MS Excel (Data Analysis Software Package). Quantitative analysis of the data includes calculation of all descriptive statistics as mean, standard deviation, percentage etc. and inferential statistics as t- test, ANOVA, two way ANOVA and intercorrelation matrix. Level of significance for statistical analysis and interpretation was considered as 0.05 level.

5.1.0 DEMOGRAPHIC FEATURES OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

Demographic features of the data are shown on certain features such as gender, age, type of college, academic stream of the of the sample included in study. It is reflected in table 8:

Table 8: Demographic Features of Pre-service Teachers

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group (20-25 years)	20 years	11	5.5%
	21 years	44	22%
	22 years	44	22%
	23 years	27	13.5%
	24 years	17	8.5%
	25 years	57	12.5%

Type of college	Govt. aided	59	29.5%
	Self-financed	141	70.5%
Academic stream	Arts	110	55%
	Commerce	28	14%
	Science	62	31%
	Total	200	

Above table indicates that total sample consists of 29.5% students studying in Govt. aided college and 70.5% in self-financed college as it reflects in the society also. Table points out that mostly (44%) B.Ed. students are age of 21-22 years; 26% students are from age of 23 and 25 years while rest are of 20 and 24 years. It is to be mentioned here, age is controlled variable here by researcher, therefore the students who were out of range of 20-25 years age, were not taken in the sample. When academic stream is discussed, it is revealed that 55% students are from arts stream, 14% students are from commerce and science stream students are 31% in sample.

5.2.0 SOFT SKILLS OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

To assess the status of soft skills in Pre-service teachers, Mean and percentage values were calculated and ranks are provided based on obtained percentage. Following table shows all related values:

Table 9: M and Percentage of scores obtained by Pre-service Teachers on Soft Skills

Main Soft Skills	Soft Skills	Max. Scores	Mean Scores	Percentage	Rank
Learning Skills	i. Critical Thinking	22	7.65	34.78	12
	ii. Creativity and Innovation	56	39.18	69.97	9
	iii. Collaboration	50	36.57	73.14	8
	iv. Communication	52	39.14	75.27	6
Literacy Skills	i. Information Literacy	13	5.32	40.92	11
	ii. Media Literacy	48	35.79	74.58	7
	iii. Technology Literacy	25	12.39	49.56	10
Life Skills	i. Flexibility and Adaptability	45	36.81	81.82	1
	ii. Leadership and Responsibility	45	36.60	81.35	2
	iii. Initiableness and Self-direction	55	43.15	78.46	4
	iv. Productivity and Accountability	55	44.57	81.04	3
	v. Social-and Cross-cultural Interaction	55	43.02	78.23	5

Table 9 unveils that pre-service teachers' life skill scores are at higher side than literacy skills and learning skills. They got more than 80 percent scores on all five life skills as Flexibility and adaptability; Leadership and responsibility; Initiativeness and self-direction; Productivity and accountability; and Social and cross-cultural interaction. Pre-service teachers performed not good on Literacy skills (Information literacy, media literacy and technological literacy), they got rank 10 and 11 on Information literacy and technological literacy respectively. Mean Scores on Learning skills of Pre-service teachers indicate that they are poor in critical thinking and creativity and innovation. They got 75.27% in collaboration skills and 73.14% in communication skills. Furthermore graph also shows the status of soft skills in pre-service teachers:

Fig 2: Graphical Representation of Soft Skills of pre-service Teachers

Based on performance of pre-service teachers shown on soft skills, five soft skills were selected for Soft Skill Enhancement Programme. Soft skills which were ranked from 6 to 11 considered in the programme. Pre-service teachers obtained least scores in critical thinking but it was not taken in the programme due to its different nature than other learning skills. This dimension is more cognitive in nature and needs long time for enhancement.

5.3.0 EFFECT OF SOFT SKILL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME ON TEACHING COMPETENCE OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

Hypothesis 1 was tested to see the effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on teaching competence of Pre-service teachers.

Hypothesis 1: There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Teaching competence of Pre-service teachers.

Both experimental and control groups were matched on Emotional intelligence, hence paired t-test was used to verify the hypothesis 1. Following were the results:

Table 10: t- test values for comparison of experimental group and controlled group on Teacher Competency scores

<i>Statistical measures</i>	<i>Values on Teacher Competency Test (Controlled Group)</i>	<i>Values on Teacher Competency Test (Experimental Group)</i>
Mean	146.12	156.67
Variance	376.85	294.93
Observations	100	100
df	99	
t Stat	4.08	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00004	
t Critical two-tail	1.66	

Table reflects that calculated t-value is found as 4.08 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance because of p value 0.00 and t-critical value 1.66. Based on t-value, it can be said that there is significant difference in teacher competency of experimental and control group. Mean score of Experimental group on teaching competency is found more than mean score of controlled group. Hence, hypothesis 1 is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. It can be interpreted that Soft Skill Enhancement programme was found effective to increase the level of teacher competency in pre-service teachers.

5.4.0 EFFECT OF SOFT SKILL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME ON TEACHER COMPETENCY OF PRESERVICE TEACHERS WITH REFERENCE TO SUBJECT STREAM

To study effect of Soft skill enhancement programme on teacher competency of pre-service teachers with refence to subject stream was done with help of ANOVA. ANOVA test was applied two times: one on control group and one on experimental group after applying Soft skill enhancement programme.

Hypothesis 2: There will be no significant difference in Teacher competence of Experimental group and Control group of Preservice teachers with reference to subject stream.

Two subhypotheses 2.1 and 2.2 were tested to verify the hypothesis 2:

Hypothesis 2.1: There will be no significant difference in Teacher competence of Control group of Preservice Teachers with reference to subject stream.

ANOVA values related to this hypothesis are given as under:

Table 11: ANOVA test values for comparison of Pre-service teachers of control group having different subject stream on Teacher competence

Groups	Count (N)	Sum	Average	Variance		
Science	26	3996	153.69	162.38		
Arts	50	7054	141.08	426.72		
Commerce	24	3562	148.41	410.94		
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	2887.50	2	1443.75	4.068	0.02	3.09
Within Groups	34421.05	97	354.85			
Total	37308.56	99				

Table 11 depicts that F value (4.068) is found significant at 0.05 level. As far as control group is concerned, science stream pre-service teachers have highest score on Teacher competency and arts stream pre-service teachers are least competent in teaching while commerce stream pre-service teachers are in between arts and science stream teachers when teacher competency is discussed. Hence, pre-service teachers showed difference in teacher competency with reference to subject stream i.e., Hypothesis 2.1 is rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

H2.2: There will be no significant difference in teacher competency of Experimental group (after treatment) of Preservice Teachers with reference to subject stream.

ANOVA values related to this hypothesis are given as under:

Table 12: ANOVA test values for comparison of Pre-service teachers of experimental group having different subject stream on Teacher competency

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
Science	35	5498	157.08	311.43		
Arts	51	7915	155.19	301.52		
Commerce	14	2210	157.85	263.36		
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	117.21	2	58.60	0.19	0.82	3.09
Within Groups	29088.5	97	299.88			
Total	29205.71	99				

Table 12 reveals that when differences are verified in case of experimental group, all subject stream's pre-service teachers have shown similar level of teaching competency because F value is found non-significant at 0.05 level of significance and mean values are more or less similar in all pre-service teachers and they could not exhibit significant difference. Hence, hypothesis was accepted.

Based on Hypothesis 2.1 rejection and 2.2 accepting, it can be said that treatment in the form of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme increased teaching competency of all stream pre-service teachers and programme finished the difference that was due to subject stream. Hence, hypothesis 2 was rejected at 0.05 level of significance and it can be interpreted that experimental and control group have significant differences on teacher competency when subject streams are considered.

5.5.0 EFFECT OF SOFT SKILL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME ON TEACHER COMPETENCY OF PRESERVICE TEACHERS WITH REFERENCE TO SELF EFFICACY

To study effect of Soft skill enhancement programme on teacher competency of pre-service teachers with refence to self-efficacy was done with help of ANOVA. ANOVA test was

applied two times: one on control group and one on experimental group after applying Soft skill enhancement programme.

Hypothesis 3: There will be no significant difference in Teacher competence of Experimental group and Control group of Preservice teachers with reference to self efficacy.

Two subhypotheses 3.1 and 3.2 were tested to verify the hypothesis 3:

Hypothesis 3.1: There will be no significant difference in Teacher Competence of Control group of Preservice Teachers with reference to self-efficacy.

ANOVA values related to this hypothesis are given as under:

Table 13: ANOVA test values for comparison of Pre-service teachers of control group having different level of Self-efficacy on Teacher competency

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average (M)</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
Low SE	20	2753	137.65	356.97		
Average SE	29	4106	141.58	590.89		
High SE	51	7703	151.03	232.27		
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	3240.05	2	1620.02	4.49	0.01	3.09
Within Groups	34941.51	97	360.22			
Total	38181.56	99				

Above table 13 indicates that F value is found significant which leads to interpret that control group of pre-service teachers are different on teacher competency when self-efficacy is referred. High self-efficacy pre service teachers exhibited high teacher competency and low self-efficacy pre service teachers showed low teacher competence. It can also be said that self-efficacy is directly related with teacher competence. Significant differences in teacher competency leads to infer that Hypothesis 3.1 is rejected at 0.01 level.

Hypothesis 3.2: There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Experimental group (after treatment) of Preservice Teachers with reference to self efficacy.

ANOVA values related to this hypothesis are given as under:

Table 14: ANOVA test values for comparison of Pre-service teachers of experimental group having different level of Self-efficacy on Teacher competence

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>		
Low SE	26	3249	124.96	525.55		
Average SE	38	5405	142.23	335.37		
High SE	36	5462	151.72	330.26		
ANOVA						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	10882.39	2	5441.19	14.22	0.00	3.09
Within Groups	37107.05	97	382.54			
Total	47989.44	99				

Table 14 reveals that Experimental group of pre-service teachers exhibited difference in Teacher competency with reference to Self-efficacy as F value is found as 14.22. Table clearly shows that high self-efficacy pre-service teachers showed high teacher competency; average self-efficacy pre-service teachers showed average and low self-efficacy pre-service teachers exhibited the low teacher competency. These differences in teacher competence of experimental group of pre-service teachers forces to reject hypothesis at 0.01 level of significance.

Based on rejection of hypothesis 3.1 and 3.2, hypothesis 3 can be rejected and concluded that there is significant difference in teacher competence of experimental and control group of pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy.

5.6.0 EFFECT OF SOFT SKILL ENHANCEMENT PROGRAMME ON SOFT SKILLS OF PRESERVICE TEACHERS

Following hypothesis was tested to see the effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Soft Skills of Pre-service teachers:

Hypothesis 4: There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Soft Skills of Preservice Teachers.

Both experimental and control groups were matched on Emotional intelligence, hence paired t-test was used to verify the hypothesis 4. Five subhypotheses were framed to verify above hypothesis 4:

Hypothesis 4.1: There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Collaboration skills.

Table15: t-value for comparison of Collaboration Skills of Pre-service Teachers of Experimental and Control Group

<i>Statistical Measures</i>	<i>Collaboration Skill (Control group)</i>	<i>Collaboration Skill (Experimental group)</i>
Mean	36.79	41.25
Variance	23.23	25.42
Observations	100	100
df	99	
t Stat	6.45	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00	
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

Table 15 reveals all the values as Mean, variance, degree of freedom and t-value for comparing collaboration skills of control group and experimental group. It is clearly visible from the table that t value is 6.45 which is highly significant because p is 0.00. p value (0.00) indicates that there is no chance of random results. Results are due to only experiment. Mean value of experimental group (41.25) is significantly higher than control group (36.79) leads to interpret that Experiment made difference in collaboration skill of Pre-service teachers. Hence, hypothesis 4.1 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4.2: There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Communication skills.

Table 16: t-value for comparison of Communication Skills of Pre-service Teachers of Experimental and Control Group

<i>Statistical Measures</i>	<i>Communication Skill (Control group)</i>	<i>Communication Skill (Experimental group)</i>
Mean	39.32	41.88
Variance	25.45	14.77
Observations	100	100
df	99	
t Stat	4.04	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00	
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

Table 16 shows all the values as Mean, variance, degree of freedom and t-value for comparing communication skills of control group and experimental group. It is clearly visible from the table that t value is 4.04 which is highly significant because p is 0.00. p value (0.00) indicates that there is no chance of random results. Results are due to only experiment. Mean value of experimental group (41.88) is significantly higher than control group (39.32) leads to interpret that Experiment made difference in communication skill of Pre-service teachers. Hence, hypothesis 4.2 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4.3: There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Information Literacy skills.

Table 17: t-value for comparison of Information Literacy Skills of Pre-service Teachers of Experimental and Control Group

<i>Statistical Measures</i>	<i>Communication Skill (Control group)</i>	<i>Communication Skill (Experimental group)</i>
Mean	5.26	7.88
Variance	4.21	5.13
Observations	100	100
df	99	
t Stat	8.27	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00	
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

Table 17 exhibits all the values as Mean, variance, degree of freedom and t-value for comparing Information literacy skills of control group and experimental group. It is clearly visible from the table that t value is 8.27 which is highly significant because p is 0.00. p value (0.00) indicates that there is no chance of random results. Results are due to only experiment. Mean value of experimental group (7.88) is significantly higher than control group (5.26) leads to interpret that Experiment made difference in Information literacy skill of Pre-service teachers. Hence, hypothesis 4.3 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4.4: There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Media Literacy skills.

Table 18: t-value for comparison of Media Literacy Skills of Pre-service Teachers of Experimental and Control Group

<i>Statistical Measures</i>	<i>Communication Skill (Control group)</i>	<i>Communication Skill (Experimental group)</i>
Mean	36.12	42.27
Variance	39.80	25.35
Observations	100	100
df	99	
t Stat	7.04	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00	
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

Table 18 demonstrates all the values as Mean, variance, degree of freedom and t-value for comparing media literacy skills of control group and experimental group. It is clearly visible from the table that t value is 7.04 which is highly significant because p is 0.00. p value (0.00) indicates that there is no chance of random results. Results are due to only experiment. Mean value of experimental group (42.27) is significantly higher than control group (36.12) leads to interpret that Experiment made difference in media literacy skill of Pre-service teachers. Hence, hypothesis 4.4 is rejected.

Hypothesis 4.5: There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Technology Literacy skills.

Table 19: t-value for comparison of Technology Literacy Skills of Pre-service Teachers of Experimental and Control Group

	<i>Technology Literacy</i>	<i>Technology Literacy</i>
Mean	12.17	17.66
Variance	26.76	17.74
Observations	100	100
df	99	
t Stat	8.26	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.00	
t Critical two-tail	1.98	

Table 19 shows all the values as Mean, variance, degree of freedom and t-value for comparing Technology literacy skills of control group and experimental group. It is clearly visible from the table that t value is 8.26 which is highly significant because p is 0.00. p value (0.00) indicates that there is no chance of random results. Results are due to only experiment. Mean value of experimental group (17.66) is significantly higher than control group (12.17) leads to interpret that Experiment made difference in Technology literacy skill of Pre-service teachers. Hence, hypothesis 4.5 is rejected.

5.7.0 CORRELATION BETWEEN SOFT SKILLS AND TEACHING COMPETENCE

To examine whether soft skill is related to teacher competence, researcher made following null hypothesis:

H5. There is no significant correlation in Soft Skills and Teaching competence of Pre-service Teachers.

To test the above said hypothesis correlation matrix is calculated between all components of soft skills and teacher competence. Soft skills include dimensions as critical thinking, creativity and innovation; collaboration skills, communication skills, information literacy skill, media literacy skill and technology literacy skill.

Table 20: Correlation matrix between components of Soft Skills and Teacher competence

	TCS	CT	CI	COL	CO	IL	ML	TL	FA	LR	IS	PA	SCI
Teacher Competency (TCS)	1												
Critical thinking (CT)	0.138	1.000											
Creativity & innovation (CI)	0.216	0.200	1.000										
Collaboration (COL)	0.119	0.139	0.337	1.000									
Communication (CO)	0.327	0.183	0.416	0.316	1.000								
information literacy (IL)	0.250	0.308	0.172	0.261	0.355	1.000							
Media Literacy (ML)	0.291	0.243	0.242	0.121	0.340	0.210	1.000						
Technology Literacy (TL)	0.206	0.238	0.150	0.218	0.416	0.517	0.336	1.000					
Flexibility & Adaptability (FA)	0.254	0.036	0.296	0.265	0.417	0.171	0.396	0.167	1.000				
Leadership &	0.269	0.186	0.278	0.238	0.457	0.258	0.361	0.250	0.483	1.000			

Responsibility (LR)													
Initiativeness & Self-direction (IS)	0.344	0.177	0.333	0.262	0.519	0.308	0.440	0.332	0.517	0.618	1.000		
Productivity & Accountability (PA)	0.292	0.065	0.226	0.164	0.421	0.172	0.374	0.255	0.519	0.580	0.566	1.000	
Social & Cross cultural Interaction (SCI)	0.287	0.111	0.364	0.232	0.390	0.171	0.281	0.266	0.481	0.609	0.555	0.572	1.000

Table 20 shows that all components of Soft skills and Teacher Competency are positively correlated because there is no negative value in table. Above table reveals that correlation between “teacher competence” and “critical thinking” is 0.138 which points out that there is very low and non-significant correlation between these two variables.

Correlation coefficient 0.216 (significant at 0.05 level) between teacher competence and creativity & innovation leads to state that there is low correlation but significant correlation between teacher competence of pre-service teachers and their creativity and innovation skill.

Further table 20 shows that teacher competence of pre-service teachers is very low and non-significantly correlated with collaboration skill ($r=0.119$) while correlation coefficient between teacher competence and communication is 0.327 which indicates about to moderate correlation and significant correlation at 0.01 level.

When correlation between teacher competence and information literacy is seen, it was found as 0.25 which tells that teacher competence is somewhat related to Information literacy and obviously significant at 0.05 level. Media literacy also shows low correlation with teacher competence of pre-service teachers with correlation coefficient value as 0.291 which is significant at 0.01 level. Also, Technology literacy and teacher competence are correlated to little extent with correlation coefficient value 0.206 significant at 0.05 level. It can be said that teacher competence is related to IMT literacy skills but association is low but significant at 0.05 level of significance.

On calculating correlation with life skills and teacher competence of pre-service teachers, it was found that teacher competence is positively correlated with Flexibility and adaptability of pre-service teacher and r between these variables is 0.206 which indicates low correlation between them. Also, other dimensions of life skills as Leadership and Responsibility, Initiativness and Self-direction, Productivity and Accountability Social and Cross-cultural Interaction with r -value

0.269, 0.344, 0.292 and 0.287 show positive and low correlation with teacher competency of Pre-service teachers. All these correlation values on life skills were significant at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, it can be said that teacher competency of Pre-service teachers is positively correlated with all dimensions of soft skills and hypothesis 5 is rejected at 0.01 level of significance.

5.8.0 PREDICTOR VARIABLES OF TEACHING COMPETENCE AMONG THE COMPONENTS OF SOFT SKILLS, EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND SELF EFFICACY

To examine predictor variables of teacher competence, researcher made following null hypothesis:

H6. There is no significant difference in the contribution of Soft Skills, Emotional intelligence and Self-efficacy in Teaching competence of Pre service Teachers.

Regression analysis was carried out to determine the predictor variables of teacher competency of Preservice teachers. To find out the variables contribution in determining teacher competence of Preservice teachers, this multiple regression analysis is the powerful tool with statisticians. Hence, to check above null hypothesis, multiple regression was applied and the obtained results are given in the following table:

Table 21: Multiple Regression Analysis for Predictor variables of Teaching competence among the selected components of Soft Skills

Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0.51							
R Square	0.26							
Adjusted R Square	0.21							
Standard Error	18.62							
Observations	200							
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	14	22730.29	1623.59	4.68	0.00			
Residual	185	64141.47	346.71					
Total	199	86871.76						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>S. Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	9.72	26.86	0.36	0.72	-43.27	62.71	-43.27	62.71
Emotional Int. (X ₁)	0.56	0.39	1.45	0.15	-0.20	1.33	-0.20	1.33

Self-Efficacy (X ₂)	0.41	0.11	3.88	0.00	0.20	0.62	0.20	0.62
Critical thinking (X ₃)	0.28	0.52	0.55	0.58	-0.74	1.31	-0.74	1.31
Creativity & innovation (X ₄)	0.00	0.22	0.02	0.99	-0.42	0.43	-0.42	0.43
Collaboration (X ₅)	-0.07	0.27	-0.26	0.80	-0.61	0.47	-0.61	0.47
Communication (X ₆)	0.45	0.33	1.37	0.17	-0.20	1.10	-0.20	1.10
Information literacy (X ₇)	0.88	0.71	1.24	0.22	-0.52	2.28	-0.52	2.28
Media Literacy (X ₈)	0.32	0.24	1.37	0.17	-0.14	0.79	-0.14	0.79
Technology Literacy (X ₉)	-0.15	0.30	-0.50	0.62	-0.74	0.44	-0.74	0.44
Flexibility & Adaptability (X ₁₀)	-0.14	0.37	-0.38	0.71	-0.86	0.58	-0.86	0.58
Leadership & Responsibility (X ₁₁)	-0.45	0.38	-1.17	0.24	-1.21	0.31	-1.21	0.31
Initiativeness & Self-direction (X ₁₂)	0.23	0.32	0.70	0.48	-0.41	0.86	-0.41	0.86
Productivity & Accountability (X ₁₃)	0.35	0.33	1.05	0.30	-0.31	1.00	-0.31	1.00
Social & Cross-cultural interaction (X ₁₄)	0.30	0.33	0.92	0.36	-0.35	0.94	-0.35	0.94

Table 21 reflects that the R i.e., multiple correlation among teacher competence and 14 predictor variables was found as 0.51 which is average and significant at 0.01 level of significance for 199 degrees of freedom. Coefficient of Multiple determination (R^2) was calculated as 0.26 and Adjusted R^2 is 0.21 which points out that 21 percent of variance in teacher competence scores accounted for by whatever is measured by 14 independent variables (12 components of soft skills, emotional intelligence, and self-efficacy) taking simultaneously, eliminating from double consideration thing that they have in common. The remaining percentage of the variance i.e., coefficient of non-determination ($1-R^2$), which is nearly 79 is still to be accounted for the variables, which are not considered in the study.

Table depicts that one variable as Self-efficacy ($\beta=0.41$) is significantly determining the teacher competence of Pre-service teachers because beta weight is significant at 0.01 level of significance. Moreover, F value was found as 4.68 significant at 0.01 level (significance $F=0.00$), hence hypothesis “There is no significant difference in the contribution of Soft Skills, Emotional intelligence and Self-efficacy in Teaching competence of Pre service Teachers” is rejected at 0.01 level of significance. On the basis of contribution of all predictor variables whether they are statistically significant or non-significant, model equation will be:

$$Y=9.72+0.56X_1+0.41X_2+0.28X_3+0.00X_4-0.07X_5+0.45X_6+0.88X_7+0.32X_8-0.15X_9-0.14X_{10}-0.45X_{11}+0.23X_{12}+0.35X_{13}+0.30X_{14}$$

When, non-significant predictor variables are eliminated and again regression analysis was done, following results were obtained:

Table 22: Multiple Regression Analysis for Significant Predictor variables of Teaching competence

<i>Regression Statistics</i>								
Multiple R	0.41							
R Square	0.17							
Adjusted R Square	0.16							
Standard Error	19.11							
Observations	200							
<i>ANOVA</i>								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	1	14566.92	14566.92	39.89	0.00			
Residual	198	72304.84	365.18					
Total	199	86871.76						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Stand. Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	75.65	10.78	7.02	0.00	54.39	96.92	54.39	96.92
Self Efficacy (X ₂)	0.59	0.09	6.32	0.00	0.41	0.78	0.41	0.78

Above table clearly explains that self-efficacy is most important and statistically significant variable which is contributing in teaching competence with beta weight 0.59. This is highly contributing variable in teaching competence. The following regression equation can be used to predict teaching competence on the basis of this analysis:

$$Y=75.65+0.56X_2$$

5.9.0 OVERVIEW OF RESULTS

To have a simplified overview of the results, a comprehensive picture is presented in table 23 specifically providing all information regarding effect of soft skill enhancement programme with reference to acceptance or rejection of hypothesis.

Table 23: Showing the hypotheses accepted or rejected

H. N.	Null Hypothesis	Accepted	Rejected
1.0	There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Teaching competence of Pre-service teachers.		√

2.0	There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group and Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to subject stream.		√
2.1	There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group of Pre-service teachers with reference to subject stream.		√
2.2	There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to subject stream.	√	
3.0	There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group and Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy.		√
3.1	There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Control group of Pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy.		√
3.2	There will be no significant difference in teacher competence of Experimental group (after treatment) of Pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy.		√
4.0	There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on specific Soft Skills of Preservice Teachers.		√
4.1	There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Collaboration skills of Preservice Teachers.		√
4.2	There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Communication skills of Preservice Teachers.		√
4.3	There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Information literacy skills of Preservice Teachers.		√
4.4	There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Media literacy skills of Preservice Teachers.		√
4.5	There will be no significant effect of Soft Skill Enhancement Programme on Technology literacy skills of Preservice Teachers.		√
5.0	There is no significant correlation in Soft Skills and Teaching competence of Pre-service Teachers.		√
6.0	There is no significant difference in the contribution of Soft Skills, Emotional intelligence, and Self-efficacy in Teaching competence of Pre service Teachers.		√

6.0.0 FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The findings of the research are systematically presented here in accordance with the objectives and concerning hypothesis as mentioned below:

1. Pre-service teachers were found very good in all five life skills in Flexibility and adaptation, Leadership and responsibility, Initiabiveness and self-direction, Productivity and accountability and Social cultural interaction. They did not perform well on learning skills and literacy skills as on life skills. They were found above average in communication skills, Media literacy skills, collaborative skills, and creativity and innovation skill. Their information literacy, technology literacy and critical thinking were found below average.
2. Soft skill enhancement programme was found effective to increase the level of teaching competence in pre-service teachers because hypothesis 1 was rejected at 0.01 level of significance ($t=4.08$).
3. Hypothesis 2.1 was rejected at 0.05 level of significance ($F=4.068$) which leads to state that control group has significant difference on teaching competence with reference to subject streams of pre-service teachers. Pre-service teachers belong to science stream got highest scores, then commerce stream got average and arts stream obtained lowest scores.

Hypothesis 2.2 was accepted ($F=0.19$) i.e., experimental group has no significant difference on teaching competence with reference to subject streams of pre-service teachers. All pre-service teachers whether they belong to any subject stream performed at somewhat similar level.

Hypothesis 2 was rejected at 0.05 level of significance and found that Soft skill enhancement program increased soft skills of preservice teachers with reference to subject stream.

4. Hypothesis 3.1 was rejected at 0.01 level of significance ($F=4.49$) which leads to interpret that control group of pre-service teachers are different on teacher competence when self-efficacy is referred. High self-efficacy pre service teachers exhibited high teacher competence and low self-efficacy pre service teachers showed low.

Experimental group showed similar findings as on control groups, and F value 14.22 hence hypothesis 3.2 was also rejected at 0.01 level of significance.

Therefore, hypothesis 3 was rejected and concluded that there is significant difference in teaching competence of control group and experimental (after treatment) of pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy and Soft skill enhancement program increased soft skills of preservice teachers with reference to self-efficacy.

5. t-values for comparing collaboration skills, communication skills, information literacy skills, media literacy skills and technology literacy skills of control group and experimental group were 6.45, 4.04, 8.27, 7.04 and 8.26 respectively. All values were found highly significant at 0.01 level and indicate that there is no chance of random results. Results are due to only experiment. Thus, hypothesis 4 is rejected. Mean value of experimental group (41.25) is significantly higher than control group (36.79) leads to interpret that Experiment made differences in all soft skills as collaboration skills, communication skills, information literacy skills, media literacy skills and technology literacy skills of Pre-service teachers.
6. It was found that all dimensions of soft skills are correlated with teaching competence. Correlation values were found in range of very low correlation to low correlation ($X_3=0.138$, $X_4=0.216$, $X_5=0.119$, $X_6=0.138$, $X_7=0.216$, $X_8=0.119$, $X_9=0.138$, $X_{10}=0.216$, $X_{11}=0.119$, $X_{12}=0.138$, $X_{13}=0.216$, $X_{14}=0.119$), but all were significantly correlated except critical thinking skill and collaboration skills. Hence hypothesis 5 was rejected at 0.05 level excluding critical thinking skill and collaboration skills.
7. In regression analysis, predictor variables of teacher competence were found out and Self-efficacy was highly significant contributor in predicting teacher competence of pre-service teachers. Hence hypothesis H6 “There is no significant difference in the contribution of Soft Skills, Emotional intelligence and Self-efficacy in Teaching competence of Pre service Teachers” is rejected at 0.01 level of significance. Variables as Emotional intelligence, critical thinking skills, creativity and innovation skills, collaboration skills, information literacy skills, media literacy skills, technology literacy skills, Flexibility and adaptation, Leadership and responsibility, Initiativeness and self-direction, Productivity and accountability and Social cultural

interaction were not found as significant predictors but they contribute in developing teaching competence.

7.0.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION OF RESULTS

Following conclusions based on the findings described in preceding pages:

1. Pre-service teachers were found below average in information literacy, technology literacy and critical thinking skills. It may be due to the reason that they are not getting training in these skills in their courses. *Krishnamurthy and Shettappanavar* (2019) also found that there is a lack of awareness among students regarding the use of various search strategies for efficient information retrieval.

They were found very good in life skills and above average in communication skills, Media literacy skills, collaborative skills, and creativity and innovation skill. This finding can be justified since pre-service teachers are mature and use these skills in their life and also get some experiences during B.Ed. program. In a similar study, *Sharma and Sharma* (2019) studied the level of soft skills and found difference between professional administration training and skills needed in the workplace. Skills learnt during training are not sufficient for workplace. *Noah and Abdul Aziz* (2020) did a systematic review and found that the graduates were lacking soft skills that are highly valued by the employers.

2. Soft skill enhancement programme was found effective to increase the level of teaching competence in pre-service teachers because hypothesis 1 was rejected at 0.01 level of significance ($t=4.08$). *Kaur and Kanojia* (2016) found that soft skills education has a significant impact on self-competence of pre-service teachers. *Shakya and Dubey* (2023) research findings suggest that the soft skills training or intervention had a very big impact on teaching competency.
3. It was found that Soft skill enhancement program increased teaching competence of preservice teachers with reference to subject stream. This finding may be justified on the fact that science students generally show best performance in comparison to other streams but soft skill training diminished this difference due to stream and all pre-service teachers exhibited increased teaching competence after getting treatment.

4. Rejection of hypothesis 3 forces to conclude that there is significant difference in teaching competence of control group and experimental (after treatment) of pre-service teachers with reference to self-efficacy and Soft skill enhancement program increased soft skills of preservice teachers with reference to self-efficacy. *Mishal* (2016) also found positive effect of a training program on self-efficacy of teacher trainees at B.Ed. level. Therefore, it may be concluded that Soft skill Enhancement programme increases teaching competency when self-efficacy is considered. Higher self-efficacy pre-service teachers showed higher teaching competence and lower self-efficacy pre-service teachers showed lower teaching competence. Programme (treatment) increased teaching competence in proportion to self-efficacy.
5. t-values for comparing collaboration skills, communication skills, information literacy skills, media literacy skills and technology literacy skills of control group and experimental group were 6.45, 4.04, 8.27, 7.04 and 8.26 respectively. All values were found highly significant at 0.01 level and indicate that there is no chance of random results. Results are due to only experiment. Thus, hypothesis 4 is rejected. Mean value of experimental group (41.25) is significantly higher than control group (36.79) leads to interpret that Experiment made differences in all soft skills as collaboration skills, communication skills, information literacy skills, media literacy skills and technology literacy skills of Pre-service teachers. This finding is obvious because Soft skill enhancement programme was rigorous programme and pre-service teachers were trained in their soft skills development. *Ahmad et.al.* (2016) also found good effect of 21st century ICT literacy model on ICT literacy skills of teacher trainees. Many researchers as *Kumar* (2017), *Ferranti & Rossi* (2020), *Abera et.al.* (2020) reported the good impact of soft skills training in their world of work.
6. It was found that all dimensions of soft skills are correlated with teaching competence. Correlation values were found in range of very low correlation to low correlation ($X_3=0.138$, $X_4=0.216$, $X_5=0.119$, $X_6=0.138$, $X_7=0.216$, $X_8=0.119$, $X_9=0.138$, $X_{10}=0.216$, $X_{11}=0.119$, $X_{12}=0.138$, $X_{13}=0.216$, $X_{14}=0.119$), but all were significantly correlated except critical thinking skill and collaboration skills. Hence hypothesis 5 was rejected at 0.05 level excluding critical thinking skill and collaboration skills. *Saleem, Warsi and Fatima* (2024) concluded on the basis of their

study that teachers with higher soft skills will likely have better teaching competencies. *Pachaiyappan and Sadayakumar* (2018) found significant positive correlation in soft skills and teaching competency. *Priya* (2011) also found that performance in different skills as communication skill, computer skill, stress management skill, organization skill, time management skill, leadership skill, interpersonal skills and team building skills of B.Ed. students significantly influence their teaching competence.

7. In regression analysis, predictor variables of teacher competence were found out and Self-efficacy was highly significant contributor in predicting teacher competence of pre-service teachers. Hence hypothesis H6 “There is no significant difference in the contribution of Soft Skills, Emotional intelligence and Self-efficacy in Teaching competence of Pre service Teachers” is rejected at 0.01 level of significance. Variables as Emotional intelligence, critical thinking skills, creativity and innovation skills, collaboration skills, information literacy skills, media literacy skills, technology literacy skills, Flexibility and adaptation, Leadership and responsibility, Initiativensness and self-direction, Productivity and accountability and Social cultural interaction were not found as significant predictors but they contribute in developing teaching competence. *Walter* (2015) recommended based on study that the teaching self-efficacy index may predict teaching competence more accurately rather than cognitive measurements. *Lauermann and König* (2016) in their study found general professional knowledge of teachers was in positive association with teaching self-efficacy.

8.0.0 EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The findings of the present study carry some important implications in education. On the basis of findings, following suggestions can be provided:

1. Pre-service teachers were found very good in all life skills. They were found above average in communication skills, Media literacy skills, collaborative skills, and creativity and innovation skill. Their information literacy, technology literacy and critical thinking were found below average. It can be suggested that teacher education institutions must focus on information literacy and technology literacy skill

development in pre-service teachers and it should be included as integral part of curriculum. Life skill enrichment should also be included in the curriculum. To develop critical thinking in pre-service teachers, assignments and activities should be assigned and teachers should use compulsorily in their teaching learning process.

2. Effectiveness of Soft Skill Enhancement program on teaching competence suggests that there should be specific space for soft skill workshops and modules in teacher education curriculum. One month workshop for soft skill development can be decided. Both theoretical and practical aspects of programme should be included to prepare them for world of work.
3. It is suggested that to finish the gaps in science, commerce and arts stream teachers competence, the Soft skill enhancement program should be implemented in teacher education programme. Also on application of this programme, pre-service teachers' teaching competence can be increased in proportion to self-efficacy.
4. It is suggested to include collaboration skills, communication skills, information literacy skills, media literacy skills and technology literacy skills in soft skill training programme essentially because special attention in form of workshops and modules would uplift the level of these skills in pre-service teachers.
5. Positive correlation of soft skills with teaching competence suggests that training of Soft skill program would increase teacher competence in pre-service teachers.
6. Self-efficacy was found highly significant contributor in predicting teacher competence of pre-service teachers. Hence, teacher education institutions should focus on self-efficacy development through different activities, personal attention, and motivation. Emotional intelligence and all soft skills considered in the research play vital role in developing teaching competence. Hence, Soft skills, self-efficacy, and emotional intelligence all should be integral part of the teacher education program.

9.0.0 DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

While considering the results emanating from the analysis of the findings, it is important to mention that the objective of the study is to deal with the conclusions from empirical data and therefore, generalizations are appropriate only when made to population seems reasonably

similar to one employed in the study. Investigators felt the following delimitations in present investigation:

1. The present study concerns itself with effectiveness of soft skill enhancement program applied online on pre-service teachers of few districts.
2. Only female pre-service teachers were taken in present research work, therefore, the results are limited only to female pre-service teachers.
3. The present study is delimited to government aided and self-financed institution pre-service teachers not to government institution pre-service teachers.

10.0.0 SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCHES

Some suggestions are presented here regarding further researches:

1. Soft skill enhancement programme can be developed for graduates and post graduate also.
2. Soft skill enhancement programme can be developed and effectiveness can be studied for BTC and B.El.Ed. students also.
3. A comprehensive Soft skill enhancement programme including all 21st century skills can be developed.
4. Soft skill study on in-service teachers can be conducted.
5. A comparative study of social skills belong to medical, engineering and social field students can be conducted.
6. Effectiveness of Soft skill enhancement program on self-competence, teaching effectiveness and other related variables can be investigated.
7. Correlational study of more variables with teaching competence and teaching effectiveness of pre-service teachers can be conducted.

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